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MORBIDITY AND MORTALITY OF PLASMODIUM IN DISTRICT MADHEPURA (BIHAR)

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Abstract

Malaria is endemic in India and its control has become a formidable task. The Planning Commission of the Government of India estimates that 26.1% of the population of India lives below the poverty line.

The radity and morbidity of Plasmodium was studied in aall the blocks of Madhepura of Bihar , it was found that the API was maximum in Gamharia (5.3) and minimumin Kumarkhand (1.9). The poverty ia an important cause of malaria.

Key words : Plasmodium, Morbidity, mortality , Madhepura

Introduction

Plasmodium is one of the important parasites for Malaria. The parasites are spread to people through the bites of infected female *Anopheles* mosquitoes, called "malaria vectors."

Malaria is an acute febrile illness. In a non-immune individual, symptoms appear 7 days or more (usually 10–15 days) after the infective mosquito bite. The first symptoms – fever, headache, chills and vomiting – may be mild and difficult to recognize as malaria. If not treated within 24 hours, *P. falciparum* malaria can progress to severe illness, often leading to death.

Children with severe malaria frequently develop one or more of the following symptoms: severe anaemia, respiratory distress in relation to metabolic acidosis, or cerebral malaria (UNICEF 2002). In adults, multi-organ involvement is also frequent. In malaria endemic areas, people may develop partial immunity, allowing asymptomatic infections to occur.

The prevalence and incidence of malaria has been shown to be very high in Madhepura District of Bihar , particularly in rural and unhygienic conditions where the disease is endemic.

There is limited knowledge on the malaria burden of the population of the selected district. The aim of this study was to assess *Plasmodium falciparum* infection, malaria-related morbidity, use of preventive measures and treatment against malaria, and physical access to health structures.

The present study is to know the mortality rates, particularly for infants and young children, and data on the prevalence of Plasmodium diseases (morbidity). It also presents information on the prevention and treatment of diseases, especially those that are life-threatening to young children. This type of information is relevant both to an assessment of the demographic situation and to the design of appropriate health policies and programmes. Mortality estimates are also useful for projecting the future size of the population.

Material and methods

The study was conducted with pre tested questionnaires and the the information also collected from Primary Health Centre o the Blocks.

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Month wise Minimum and Maximum Temperature (⁰C) of Madhepura District

Month	Max	Min
January	20.45	10.61
February	27.17	13.8
March	31.25	17.45
April	34.63	21.29
May	38.00	24.86
June	38.2	27.81
July	33.64	25.61
August	34.00	25.76
September	34.16	25.89
October	33.64	23.23
November	28.88	18.16
December	24.35	12.88

Table 2: Annual Parasitic index of the different blocks of the District

	Block	Total Population	Malaria positive cases	API
1	Gamharia	82522	4435	5.374
2	Singheshwar	134159	4352	3.243
3	Ghailarh	91818	3421	3.725
4	Madhepura	191375	4231	2.210
5	Shankerpur	106222	4216	3.969
6	Kumarkhand	243629	4652	1.909
7	Murliganj	185631	4562	2.457
8	Gwalpara	126020	6657	5.282
9	Biharianj	135534	4562	3.365
10	Kisanganj	189159	4251	2.247
11	Puraini	104436	5250	5.027
12	Alamnagar	175401	4985	2.842
13	Chausa	152693	5250	3.438

Table 3: Morbidity and Mortality due to plasmodium in different block of the Madhepura district

	Block	Total Population	Blood sample examined	Positive detected	Morbidity %	Mortality	Mortality %
1	<u>Gamharia</u>	82522	4950	4435	89.595	5	0.112
2	<u>Singheshwar</u>	134159	4985	4352	87.301	3	0.068
3	<u>Ghailarh</u>	91818	3758	3421	91.032	4	0.116
4	<u>Madhepura</u>	191375	4632	4231	91.342	0	0
5	<u>Shankerpur</u>	106222	5489	4216	76.808	0	0
6	<u>Kumarkhand</u>	243629	5251	4652	88.592	0	0
7	<u>Murliganj</u>	185631	5258	4562	86.763	5	0.109
8	<u>Gwalpara</u>	126020	7298	6657	91.216	6	0.090
9	<u>Biharianj</u>	135534	5264	4562	86.664	3	0.0657
10	<u>Kisanganj</u>	189159	4325	4251	98.289	2	0.047
11	<u>Puraini</u>	104436	5498	5250	95.489	2	0.038
12	<u>Alamnagar</u>	175401	5243	4985	95.079	3	0.060
13	<u>Chausa</u>	152693	5982	5250	87.763	5	0.095

Table: 4 Categorization of the blocks on the basis of API

Sl.no	Block	API	Category on the basis of API
1	Gamharia	5.37	Moderately high region of incidence
2	Singheshwar	3.24	Moderate region of incidence
3	Ghailarh	3.72	Moderate region of incidence
4	Madhepura	2.21	Moderate region of incidence
5	Shankerpur	3.96	Moderate region of incidence
6	Kumarkhand	1.9	Low region of incidence
7	Murliganj	2.45	Moderate region of incidence
8	Gwalpara	5.28	Region of moderately high incidence
9	Bihariganj	3.36	Moderate region of incidence
10	Kisanganj	2.24	Moderate region of incidence
11	Puraini	5.02	Region of moderately high incidence
12	Alamnagar	2.84	Moderate region of incidence
13	Chausa	3.43	Moderate region of incidence

Table 5: Age wise & sex wise Death report of Malaria in Madhepura

Age group			
Years	Male	Female	Total
0-10	14	9	23
11-20	2	8	10
21-30	3	8	11
31-40	0	1	1
41-50	3	4	7
51-60	Nil	Nil	Nil
> 60	Nil	Nil	Nil
Total	22	30	52

Conventional methods of classifying causes of death suggest that about 70% of the deaths of children (aged 0-4 years) worldwide are due to diarrhoeal illness, acute respiratory infection, malaria, and immunizable diseases (UNICEF 2002). The role of malnutrition in child mortality is not revealed by these conventional methods, despite the long-standing recognition of the synergism between malnutrition and infectious diseases. which could be attributed to the potentiating effects of malnutrition in infectious disease. The results from 53 developing countries with nationally representative data on child weight-for-age indicate that 56% of child deaths were attributable to malnutrition's potentiating effects, and 83% of these were attributable to mild-to-moderate as opposed to severe malnutrition(IRRI2002). For individual countries, malnutrition's total potentiating effects on mortality ranged from 13% to 66%, with at least three-quarters of this arising from mild-to-moderate malnutrition in each case. These results show that malnutrition has a far more powerful impact on child mortality than is generally appreciated(Sharma 2003) and suggest that strategies involving only the screening and treatment of the severely malnourished will do little to address this impact.

Vector-borne diseases are transmitted typically by the bite of an infected arthropod. The arthropod could be something rather familiar like a mosquito, tick, or black fly. Or it might be a less familiar species such as an African Tsetse fly or copepod. These arthropods that carry and transmit diseases are known as **vectors**. Other non-arthropod vectors can include rodents such as rats, certain bats, a species of aquatic snail, and several species of wild birds. Different vectors carry different diseases such as malaria, dengue, encephalitis, African sleeping sickness, and yellow fever.

In general, climate plays an important role in the seasonal pattern or temporal distribution of diseases that are carried and transmitted through vectors because the vector animals often thrive in particular climate conditions(Bekele etal 2011) For example, warm and wet environments are excellent places for mosquitoes to breed. If those breeding mosquitoes happen to be a species that can transmit disease and if there is an infected population in the region, then the disease is more likely to spread in that area. Because they are sensitive to climate, the distribution and number of vectors is also affected by climate change. According to the IPCC Fourth Assessment Report, climate change has already altered the distribution of some disease vectors. There is

evidence that the geographic range of ticks and mosquitoes that carry disease has changed in response to climate change. Ticks have extended their range north in Sweden and Canada and into higher altitudes in the Czech Republic. While future climate change is expected to continue to alter the distribution of disease vectors, it is important to recognize that there are several other factors (such as changes in land use, population density, and human behavior) that can also change the distribution of disease vectors as well as the extent of infection.

The incidence of malaria varies from place to place and at different times. Such variations are very common in Madhepura. There are areas where the incidence of malaria is high and other areas where the incidence is low, and some areas are malaria free. In some communities, malaria transmission lasts for several months or happens throughout the year, and in other areas it is very brief.

Climate affects the natural distribution of malaria in Ethiopia and elsewhere in the world (Huang et.al 2011). The three main climatic factors that directly affect malaria transmission are *temperature*, *rainfall* and *relative humidity* (the amount of moisture in the air). Several non-climatic factors, including differences between human hosts, human migration, and development projects, can also affect the pattern of malaria transmission and the severity of the problem.

Climatic factors greatly influence the pattern and level of malaria transmission in Ethiopia, in Africa and the world. The most important climatic factors that directly affect malaria transmission are temperature, rainfall and humidity (Huang et.al 2011).

The ranges of minimum and maximum temperature greatly affect the development of the malaria parasite and its mosquito vector, which determines malaria transmission.

Temperature affects the life cycle of the malaria parasite. The time required for the parasite to complete its development in the gut of the mosquito is about 10 days, but it can be shorter or longer than that depending on the temperature. As the temperature *decreases*, the number of days necessary to complete the development *increases* for a given *Plasmodium* species. *P. vivax* and *P. falciparum* have the shortest development cycles and are therefore more common than *P. ovale* and *P. malariae*.

The time needed for the parasite to complete its development in the mosquito, decreases to less than 10 days as temperature increases from 21°C to 27°C, with 27°C being the optimum. The

maximum temperature for parasite development is 40°C. Below 18°C, the life cycle of *P. falciparum* in the mosquito body is limited. The minimum temperatures are between 14–19°C, with *P. vivax* surviving at lower temperatures than *P. falciparum*. Malaria transmission in areas colder than 18°C can sometimes occur because the *Anopheles* often live in houses, which tend to be warmer than the outside temperature.

Development of the mosquito larva also depends on temperature – it develops more quickly at higher temperatures. Higher temperatures also increase the number of blood meals taken and the number of eggs laid by the mosquitoes, which increases the number of mosquitoes in a given area.

The minimum temperature for mosquito development is between 8–10°C; the optimum temperature is 25–27°C, and the maximum temperature for is 40°C.

Altitude (elevation above sea level) is one of the most important factors that determine the pattern of malaria transmission in Ethiopia. Altitude in Ethiopia varies from 100 metres below sea level to more than 4,000 metres above sea level. Altitude influences the distribution and transmission of malaria indirectly, through its effect on temperature. As altitude increases, temperature decreases, so highlands are colder and lowlands are warmer.

Anopheline mosquitoes breed in water, so the right amount of rainfall is often important for them to breed. Different anopheline mosquitoes prefer different types of water bodies in which to breed. Generally, water collections that support vector breeding appear mainly after the rains, and therefore malaria transmission is highest following the rainy season.

It is important to note that the anopheline mosquitoes that transmit malaria do not breed in foul-smelling polluted water. Of course, too much rainfall can flush away breeding habitats temporarily, but mosquitoes start breeding as soon as the rain stops. In most cases, flushing has a bigger impact on vector breeding habitats in the highlands and hilly areas than in the lowland plains. Not all water collections are suitable for the mosquito life cycle. In Ethiopia, rain water collections are the most important breeding ground, as the anopheline mosquitoes prefer to breed in fresh water collections created after the rainy season.

There are also places where *less* rainfall and drought can favour mosquito breeding and malaria transmission. Such places are usually covered by vegetation throughout the year and streams and rivers often flow rapidly. When the rains fail or are delayed, the flow of streams is interrupted and pooling occurs along the stream. Pooling creates a favourable environment for mosquito breeding. Malaria vectors mainly breed in stagnant water collections, rarely in slightly moving waters and never in rapidly flowing rivers and streams.

In drier areas, rainfall can also affect malaria transmission indirectly through its effect on humidity. Vegetation cover increases after rainfall, which in turn increases the relative humidity of the environment. The effect of humidity on malaria transmission is considered below. The average rainfall and water logging is common phenomena may be an important reason for malaria in the project area.

Relative humidity refers to the amount of moisture in the air, expressed as a percentage; (0% humidity would mean the air is completely free of moisture and 100% humidity would mean the air is completely saturated with moisture). Relative humidity affects malaria transmission through its effect on the activity and survival of mosquitoes, its need to live at least 8–10 days to be able to transmit malaria.

Mosquitoes survive better under conditions of high humidity. They also become more active when humidity rises. This is why they are more active and prefer feeding during the night – the relative humidity of the environment is higher at night. If the average monthly relative humidity is below 60%, it is believed that the life of the mosquito is so short that very little or no malaria transmission is possible.

The incidence of malaria is generally lower in urban areas than in rural areas (Howard 1970). There are a number of reasons for this:

- While there is plenty of space for vector breeding in rural villages, mosquito breeding sites in urban areas are limited because more space is covered by houses.
- People in urban areas may have more access to health care and malaria prevention strategies than people in rural villages.

However, rapid urbanisation of areas within or on the outskirts of urban centres is commonly done in an uncontrolled fashion without thought or planning. The settlers are mainly migrant

workers from rural villages. Conditions are crowded; housing is often of poor quality or is of temporary construction; and the provision of health care and sanitation is often inadequate.

The present study reflects that the disease is a multiple phenomena & that various factors co-mingle in time & space for its incidence. The future strategy of eradication of malaria is to be decided very thoughtfully in order to get rid off this scourge from the state. It is the natural environment that has created suitable conditions for this disease. We are unable to change the environment but the man-made malaria can be eliminated by constant vigil on all fronts & more integrated control & eradication measures should be implemented in the campaign against malaria. The following suggestions deserve serious considerations: -

Fight against mosquito vectors should go on. Replacing chemical control (snow etal 1999) by alternative methods means replacing a simple, simple procedure by multiple procedures, each demands expert knowledge.

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